

ANALYZE THE MARKETING EFFICIENCY, SHARE AND MARGIN OF (NPH-X4) HYBRID PADDY IN ROHTAS DISTRICT OF BIHAR

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Abstract

The present study entitled "Analyze the marketing efficiency, share and margin of (NPH-X4) Hybrid Paddy in Rohtas District of Bihar" was undertaken to study overview, marketing cost, margins and price spread, problems in different supply chains and preferences of farmers in Rohtas District of Bihar. Combinations of purposive stratified and random sampling technique were used for market functionaries and farmer selection required for the purpose of study. The data for the present study pertained to Agricultural year 2022- 2023. Secondary data was collected from secondary sources like marketing committee office APMC, Rohtas, Centre for Monitoring Indian Economy (CMIE), India state etc. The data on family composition, participation of family members in farming activities, input-output coefficients in the production of hybrid paddy, yields, marketing costs, and prices collected from farmers and value addition, market margin and marketing costs were collected from market functionaries using pre tested questionnaires of these purposes. The data collected was subjected to various analytical tools apart from simple averages. Cost concepts were used to determine cost of market of hybrid paddy, market margin and price spread of hybrid paddy. Two important Supply chains were identified which operate through APMC Rohtas, Supply chain-I the produce is traded from Producer through Trader, Wholesaler, Retailer, and finally delivered to consumer and Supply chain the produce is traded from Producer, through Trader, Wholesaler, Retailer, and finally delivered to consumer. In both Supply chains price is determined in presence of Commission agents, Producers, and Traders or Processors. The study on problems associated with marketing of hybrid paddy shows that Cultivation Problem and knowledge barrier are two major problems according to farmers.

Keywords: Marketing cost, Market margin, Functionaries, Supply chain, Trader,

Introduction:

India is world's leading producer of white rice, accounting for 20 % of overall production. Rice is India's prominent crop, and staple food for the native population of eastern and southern part of the country. The country has biggest area of fertile land under rice cultivation. Moreover, this country has the largest area under rice cultivation. As it is one of the principal food crops. It is, in fact, the dominant crop of the country. India is one of the leading producers of this crop. Rice is the basic food crop and being a tropical plant, it flourishes comfortably in a hot and humid climate. Rice is mainly grown in rain-fed areas that receive heavy annual rainfall. That is why it is fundamentally a kharif crop in India. It demands a temperature of around 25 degrees Celsius and above, and rainfall of more than 100 cm. Rice is also grown through irrigation in those areas that receive comparatively less rainfall. Rice is the staple food of eastern and southern parts of India.

Rice can be cultivated by different methods based on the type of region. But in India, traditional methods are still in use for harvesting rice. The fields are initially ploughed and fertilizer is applied which typically consists of cow dung, and then the field is smoothed. The seeds are transplanted by hand and then through proper irrigation, the seeds are cultivated. Rice grows on a variety of soils like silts, loams and gravels. It can tolerate alkaline as well as acid soils. However, clayey loam is well suited to the raising of this crop. Actually, the clayey soil can be easily converted into the mud in which rice seedlings can be transplanted easily. Proper care has to be taken as this crop thrives if the soil remains wet and is underwater during its growing years. Rice fields should be level and should have low mud walls for retaining water. In the plain areas, excess rainwater is allowed to inundate the rice fields and flow slowly. Rice raised in the well-watered lowland areas is known as lowland or wet rice. In the hilly areas, slopes are cut into terraces for the cultivation of rice. Thus, the rice grown in the hilly areas is known as dry or upland rice. The yield of upland rice per hectare is comparatively less than that of wet rice.

Indian agriculture has come a long way since the Green Revolution of the late 1960s. India presents an interesting scenario: both GDP and food grain production in the country have risen faster than the growth in population over the last 50 years. But now the situation is becoming alarming as the agricultural growth has been static in recent years. The enormity of the problem is indicated by the fact that the

during the 10-year period 1997-98 to 2006-07, our food grain production has grown at an average annual rate of only 1%. Interestingly, while the nation rejoices at the recovery in food grain production at 241.6 million tons in 2010-11 with 6.6% growth, the fact remains that it is only marginal increase over the production of 233.88 million tons in 2008-09. The total demand estimate for food grains was touch 280 million tons by 2020. To achieve the forgoing amount of production a growth rate of 4% in agricultural sector has to be maintained over next 15 years. It is very important that the economic growth fosters social equity.

Thus, the present-day study was an effort in direction of study in all aspects of supply chain management of rice and to identify the problems faced by supply chain management of rice and overall view of exploring the possibility and potentialities for bring about the require improvement.

Materials and Methods:

The study entitled "Analyze the marketing efficiency, share and margin of (NPH-X4) Hybrid Paddy in Rohtas District of Bihar" was undertaken to assess cost of marketing channels of Hybrid Paddy in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh.

Study design:

Multistage stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the present investigation to select the ultimate unit of the sample.

Place of the study

Out of 38 districts, Rohtas district of Bihar was selected purposively for the present study.

Sample:

Total 200 respondents were selected from the Rohtas district of Bihar by following simple random sampling procedure.

Data collection:

The primary data will be collected from customer and dealers by the help of a structured questionnaire and Secondary data will be collected from past records maintained by Paddy dealers of the study area.

Analysis of Data:

The collected data was interpreted and arranged by statistical package for social sciences-16 (SPSS 16) which was specially designed for this purpose.

Results and Discussion:

The study entitled "Analyze the marketing efficiency, share and margin of (NPH-X4) Hybrid Paddy in Rohtas District of Bihar"

was undertaken to assess the marketing efficiency, share and margin of Hybrid Paddy in Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh. The results are given under the following heads:

Table 1:

S. No	Particular	Rs.	Percentage
1	Net price received by producer	3570	76.98
2	Marketing cost incurred by producer	24	0.51
3	Price Paid by trader	3594	77.50
4	Expenses incurred by trader	72	1.55
5	Margin of trader	56	1.20
6	Price paid by wholesaler	3722	81.34
7	Expenses incurred by wholesaler	45	0.97
8	Margin of wholesaler	336	7.24
9	Price paid by processor	4103	88.48
10	Total marketing cost	141	3.04
11	Total marketing margin	392	8.47
12	Consumer price	4637	100

Fig 1: Constraints in Adoption of Hybrid Paddy:

Table 2: Constraints in Adoption of Hybrid Paddy

S. No	Constraints	Farmers Response	Percent	Ranking
1	Cultivation Problem	50	25	1
2	Knowledge Barrier	30	15	2
3	Awareness	24	12	3
4	Motivation	20	10	5
5	Climatic Problems	18	9	7
6	Disease/pest attack	16	8	8
7	High price of seed	22	11	4
8	Quality of seed	20	10	6
	Total	200	100	

Table shows constraints reported by selected farmers for adoption of hybrid seeds of paddy in the study area. Major constraint reported by the sample farmers was cultivation problem (25%), followed by Knowledge Barrier about improved seeds (15%), lack of awareness (12%), motivation (10%) climatic problem (9%), disease / pest attack (8%). high price of seed (11%) and quality of seed (10%). Thus, these constraints should be minimizing to augment adoption of production technology and productivity per unit of cropped area.

Summary and Conclusion:

Incentive to the field staff: - the field staff has less salary so if company provides incentive in form of commotions on FBS coupon so they will do work more effective

High price of the product: - As the variety is new people are not aware they don't have knowledge of its benefit so they are not ready to pay more money for a new variety .so initially its price should be reduced.

Incentive to dealer and distributor: dealers and distributors margin is less as compared to other companies so their margin should be increased

Number of field employees at field level should be increased by the company to cover more area.

More demonstrations needed this method properly conveys our message to the farmers and this should be done authentically.

Initially we should provide some extra facilities like fertilizer with each bag of seed. This will attract the farmers.

Some big farmers or big people of the local area should support our product because common people are more influenced by experienced people than the company manager.

Fig 2: Constraints in Adoption of Hybrid Paddy

Conclusion:

On the basis of results of the present study the following conclusions were as under. The total market sale of Hybrid Paddy Seed was 90 tons in Sasaram block of Rohtas district during the period of survey. On the basis seed quantity of Paddy in Rohtas district of Bihar. the top 5 majors' companies among the various seed companies dealing with hybrid paddy seed in the market are Bayer Crop Science, Nuziveedu Seeds, VNR Seeds, J.K. Seeds, Kaveri seeds. The market share of major players in hybrid paddy seed marketing was Bayer Crop Science is on top, followed by Nuziveedu Seed then VNR Seed, J.K. Seed, and Kaveri seeds respectively. The market potential of hybrid paddy seed in the Sasaram block of Rohtas district were 63.67% (Hybrid) followed by 36.32% (Research seed and local varieties) respectively. Mostly the Hybrid Paddy Seeds was sold in 1kg and 3 kg packet priced were ranged from as. 210 to As, 350/a. Farmers were giving more response with the other scheme like scratch coupons, free gift, provided by the companies for the marketing in the district. The average size of holding of the respondents (hybrid paddy growers) was 2-3 Hectare. In Rabi season wheat were reported as the major crops occupying the area 32.89 per cent over across cultivated area. The majority of hybrid paddy growers having literacy level up to middle and high school education.

References:

1. Ahuja, S. S., Pramod Rikhi, Baldev Dogra. 2007. Economies of harvesting and threshing of wheat and paddy

in Northern India. Journal of Agricultural Engineering (New Delhi). 44(2): 14-19.

2. Abey, P. Philp, (2008). "An analytical study of market integration hypothesis for natural rubber cultivation of Kerala". ICFAI University Journal of Agricultural Economics.
3. Aloyce, R.M., Kaliba, Hugo, V. And Wilfred M., 2000, Factors affecting adoption of improved maize seeds and use of inorganic fertilizer for maize production in the intermediate and lowland zones of Tanzania. J. Agric. Appl. Econ., 32(1):35-47.
4. Achchuthan, S. And Kajanathan, R., 2012, A study on value chain analysis in Paddy Sector: Special Reference to Kilinochchi District, Sri Lanka. Glob. J. Manage. Bus. Res., 12(18): 13-22.
5. Bhide, S., Chowdhury, A., Heady, E. O. And Muralidharan, M. A., 1981, Structural changes in an agriculture assembling markets: A case study of recant market in Mangalore, Karnataka state. Ind. J. Agric. Econ., 36(2): 25-34.
6. Brumfield, R. O., Adekya, A. O. And Liminger., 1993, Consumer tastes, preference and behavior in purchasing of fresh tomatoes. J. Am. Soc. Hort. Sci., 118 (3): 433-438